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FORMULATION OF COMPOSITIONS AND THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS OF ALLOYS OF THE INTERMETALLIC SYSTEM InTe-CoSe

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Abstract

The phase diagram of the InTe-CoSe system was constructed using the basic methods of physicochemical analysis. It was found that the system is quasi-binary, and its state diagram is of a simple eutectic type. A region of solid solutions based on InTe was found, which at 300 K has a boundary of up to ~5 mol%. Some thermodynamic functions such as standard heat capacity, entropy, enthalpy, and free energy of formation of the $(\text{InTe})_{0.95}(\text{CoSe})_{0.05}$ solid solution was calculated. The least squares method is used to construct polynomial equations for equilibrium lines on the phase diagram, which show the dependence of alloy compositions on temperature.

Keywords: phase diagram, thermodynamic functions, polynomial equations, stable solutions.

It is well known that the InTe compound belongs to the class of promising materials for thermoelectric energy sources [3]. Therefore, obtaining and studying new alloys based on it is a topical problem. For this reason, we have synthesized various compounds in the InTe-CoSe system and studied their physicochemical properties.

Extensive information about the properties of the InTe is available in [5]. The CoSe compound melts congruently at 1055 °C [7]. The width of the homogeneous region of this composition at 600 °C is in the range of 50.4-57 at% Se; therefore, a region of retrograde solubility of the solid solution is formed on the basis of the compound. Within this homogeneous region, depending on the composition and temperature, there is a transition from a hexagonal (NiAs type) to a monoclinic crystal structure.

The synthesis of alloys of the InTe-CoSe system was carried out from high-purity elements of indium, cobalt, selenium and tellurium by the direct ampoule method at a temperature of ~1373 K. To achieve an equilibrium state, the resulting ingots were subjected to long-term homogenizing annealing at ~803 K for 480 hours. The resulting polycrystalline samples had a dense bulk structure with a non-metallic luster.

Thermographic (THERMOSCAN-5), X-ray phase (D2PHASER with a nickel filter), microstructural analyzes and microhardness measurement (ViewMET and

Micromet S101)) were carried out according to the method given in [2].

Using the methods from [2], we constructed the phase diagram of the InTe-CoSe system (Fig. 1). The diagram is of the simple eutectic type and has a solid solution region based on InTe. The boundary of this region at room temperature reaches 5 mol%. From the phase diagram, one can conclude that the system is quasi-binary. The liquidus lines in the diagram converge at the invariant point at ~833 K in the composition of ~18 mol% CoSe.

Figure 2 shows an X-ray pattern of a 5 mol% CoSe solid solution of the presented system. Since this alloy is formed on the basis of tetragonal InTe, it can be assumed that this compound also crystallizes in a tetragonal lattice. As can be seen, the main intensity lines in the diffraction pattern are the same as in the original InTe compound (Fig. 2).

From measurements of microhardness, it was found that the value of microhardness in the region of solid solutions increases and, for the composition with 5 mol% CoSe reaches ~2250 MPa. If we take into account that the microhardness of unalloyed InTe is 960 MPa, then we can conclude that the detected solid solutions are substitutional solid solutions.

The pycnometric density value of all alloys of the system adequately varies from the InTe density value ($\rho=6.29 \text{ g/cm}^3$) to the CoSe density value ($\rho=6.85 \text{ g/cm}^3$).

Fig. 1. Phase diagram of the InTe-CoSe system

Fig. 2. Diffractogram of $(\text{InTe})_{0.95}(\text{CoSe})_{0.05}$ solid solution (intensities that refer to InTe are shown by perpendicular lines)

It can be seen from the constructed state diagram that a limited region of solid solutions based on InTe is formed in the system. To confirm the stability of this phase, i.e. regularity of these solid solutions, the main thermodynamic functions of $(\text{InTe})_{1-x}(\text{CoSe})_x$ alloys are calculated.

In order to calculate the atomization energy H_s , it is necessary to know the H_s values of the initial components. According to the results of our research, $H_s(\text{InTe})=134.01$ kJ/mol. For CoSe

$$H_s(\text{CoSe}) = \frac{H_s(\text{Co}) + H_s(\text{Se})}{m}$$

where m is the number of atoms in a molecule. Therefore, $H_s(\text{CoSe})=215.78$ kJ/mol and $H_s((\text{InTe})_{0.95}(\text{CoSe})_{0.05})=0.95H_s(\text{InTe})+0.05H_s(\text{CoSe})=138.1$ kJ/mol.

Further, using the thermodynamic data of the initial components, the values of the standard heat capacity, entropy, enthalpy, and free energy of formation of the $(\text{InTe})_{0.95}(\text{CoSe})_{0.05}$ solid solution are calculated.

According to the Neumann-Kopp method [6], to calculate the standard heat capacity of $(\text{InTe})_{0.95}(\text{CoSe})_{0.05}$ we can write:

$$C_{p298}((\text{InTe})_{0.95}(\text{CoSe})_{0.05}) = \\ = 0.95C_{p298}(\text{InTe}) + 0.05C_{p298}(\text{CoSe}).$$

In [6], the standard heat capacity of InTe is 47.82 J/(mol·K), and for CoSe we calculate: $C_{p298}(\text{CoSe}) = C_{p298}(\text{Co}) + C_{p298}(\text{Se}) = 50.3$ J/(mol·K). Thus, the standard heat capacity of the $(\text{InTe})_{0.95}(\text{CoSe})_{0.05}$ solid solution is $C_{p298} = 45.7$ J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹.

At the same time, according to the empirical formula of Magnus-Lindemann [4]

$$C_p = C_V + \frac{T^{3/2}}{T_{melt}^{3/2}}, \quad (1)$$

from which it is easy to estimate the isochoric heat capacity C_V . This expression reflects the relationship between the number of atoms in a molecule and the melting point. In a simple case, such a relationship is represented as [4]

$$C_p = m \left(5,29 + \frac{RT}{T_{melt}} \right). \quad (2)$$

The isochoric heat capacity can also be calculated using the Magnus-Lindemann method [10], knowing the characteristic Debye temperature θ_D , which, in turn, is estimated by the formula

$$\theta'_D = \theta_D \left(\frac{T'_{melt}}{T_{melt}} \right)^{1/2}, \quad (3)$$

where θ'_D is the Debye temperature calculated on the basis of the values of the melting point of the compound itself and the chemical elements that make up this compound, θ_D is the Debye temperature of the chemical element, T'_{melt} is the melting point of the compound, T_{melt} is the melting point of the chemical element. It should be noted that the Debye method is based on the quantum concept of vibrations of atoms in the crystal lattice of a solid.

Substituting the corresponding data from [8, 10], we obtain $\theta'_D(\text{InTe}) = 150.2$ K, $\theta'_D(\text{CoSe}) = 484$ K. Then $\theta'_D((\text{InTe})_{0.95}(\text{CoSe})_{0.05}) = 166.89$ K.

According to [10], to determine C_V , the value $(\theta'_D)/(T, \text{K})$ or $(\theta'_D)/298$ is required. Considering this, we find: $C_V(\text{InTe}) = 24.64$ J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹, $C_V(\text{CoSe}) = 24.05$ J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹, $C_V((\text{InTe})_{0.95}(\text{CoSe})_{0.05}) = 24.51$ J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹.

The entropy of the initial compounds and the solid solution was calculated by the Kelly method [6]:

$$\sum S_{298}^0(\text{InTe}) = S_{298}^0(\text{In}) + S_{298}^0(\text{Te}), \\ \sum S_{298}^0(\text{CoSe}) = S_{298}^0(\text{Co}) + S_{298}^0(\text{Se}).$$

It was found that $\sum S_{298}^0(\text{InTe}) = 107.54$ J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹, $\sum S_{298}^0(\text{CoSe}) = 72.29$ J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹ and $\sum S_{298}^0((\text{InTe})_{0.95}(\text{CoSe})_{0.05}) = 105.78$ J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹.

Knowing the value of the isobaric heat capacity, we can calculate the standard entropy:

$$S_{298}^0 = K_H m (M/C_{p298})^{1/3},$$

where M is the molar mass of the compound, K_H is the coefficient (Hertz constant), which depends on the degree of ionicity of the chemical bond. For chalcogenides $K_H = 4$. Given that the number of atoms m in our solid solution is 4, the standard entropy will be equal to $S_{298}^0((\text{InTe})_{0.95}(\text{CoSe})_{0.05}) = 128.58$ J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹.

The entropy of formation of a solid solution can be calculated using the following formula:

$$\Delta S_{298}^0 = S_{298}^0 - \nu_t \sum S_{298}^0,$$

ν_t is the stoichiometric coefficient, which can be taken equal to 1. Then $\Delta S_{298}^0((\text{InTe})_{0.95}(\text{CoSe})_{0.05}) = 22.8$ J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹.

The enthalpy of formation of the initial components of the system can be taken from [11], where $\Delta H_{298}^0(\text{InTe}) = -72240$ J/mol and $\Delta H_{298}^0(\text{CoSe}) = -79380$ J/mol. For the solid solution $(\text{InTe})_{0.95}(\text{CoSe})_{0.05}$ $\Delta H_{298}^0 = -72597$ J/mol.

The Gibbs-Helmholtz equation [12] makes it possible to calculate the free energy of formation:

$$\Delta G_{298}^0 = \Delta H_{298}^0 - 298 \Delta S_{298}^0.$$

It was determined that $\Delta G_{298}^0((\text{InTe})_{0.95}(\text{CoSe})_{0.05}) = -65802.6$ J/mol. The “-” sign indicates the stability of the composition; therefore, the solid solution under study can be attributed to the class of stable solutions.

The upper boundary of the solid solution region and the eutectic line can be taken as the solidus of the phase diagram of the InTe-CoSe system. Denoting the lines of liquidus and solidus conditionally with the letters l, m, n and k, a formulation was made (Fig. 1). For this, polynomial equations obtained by the least squares method were used, which, being the third and fourth degrees, contain information about the composition and temperature boundaries of each line [9]. Here is how one can represent the composed polynomial equations:

$$x = aT^3 + bT^2 + cT + d, \\ x = aT^4 + bT^3 + cT^2 + dT + e.$$

The last numbers d and e in the equations are constant coefficients. The standard error coefficient (R) was also taken into account when processing equations on a computer.

Thus, given the compositions and temperatures in the phase diagram, for the “l” curve:

$$\text{liq} \\ 0 < x < 86, 833 \text{ K} < T < 970 \text{ K}. \\ \text{liq} + \alpha$$

For the other part of the liquidus curve:

$$\text{liq} \\ 86 < x < 100, 833 \text{ K} < T < 1328 \text{ K}. \\ \text{liq} + \text{CoSe}$$

For the “n” curve,

here α denotes the solid solution based on InTe.

The “h” curve is the eutectic line of the phase diagram and its coordinates are:

If these quantities are substituted into polynomial equations and solved, then the compositions of alloys of the InTe-CoSe system and their melting points and crystallization temperatures can be found over the entire concentration range. At the same time, taking the liquidus lines of the InTe-CoSe system as part of a parabola, and using the equations of the parabola [1], one can calculate them mathematically.

Thus, calculations of the thermodynamic parameters of the homogeneous composition $(\text{InTe})_{0.95}(\text{CoSe})_{0.05}$ show that these solutions are stable, which is an important factor in solving applied problems.

By applying hypothetical equations to the experimental phase diagram of InTe-CoSe, it is possible to find mathematically the compositions, melting and crystallization temperatures, and important coordinates of the invariant points.

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